

Lattice Boltzmann Simulation of Viscous Flow Over a Circular Cylinder for Reynolds Numbers of 20 to 200

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Abstract—With recent advancements in High Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructure and parallel computing, the Lattice-Boltzmann method has emerged as an efficient and parallelizable algorithm for Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) applications. The present study investigates the viscous flow over a circular cylinder as a validation test case using the Lattice-Boltzmann Method (LBM) with OpenLB flow solver. Parallel numerical simulations are performed for the prediction of the drag coefficient and Strouhal number at different Reynolds numbers. Flow simulations are performed at Reynolds numbers ranging from 20 to 200 to observe both steady-state and unsteady flow characteristics by vortex shedding. Aerodynamic drag coefficient and Strouhal number are compared with previous experimental and numerical studies in the literature. The accuracy and reliability of the LBM method for simulations of separated vortical flows around a circular cylinder at low Reynolds numbers are discussed in detail. Computational cost analyses of the parallel simulations are also presented and discussed.

Index Terms—Lattice Boltzmann Method, CFD, 2D Circular Cylinder, Vortex Shedding

I. INTRODUCTION

Flow over a circular cylinder has been a subject of extensive study in fluid mechanics for almost a century, ranging from inviscid, incompressible flow to separated viscous flows for benchmarking new Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) solvers. Despite its simple geometry, the flow around a cylinder has complex flow features such as vortex shedding which is an important unsteady flow phenomenon that exists for many engineering problems depending on the Reynolds number. Similar separated vortical flows around wind turbine airfoils are still hard to predict accurately. Use of thick airfoils in wind turbine blades and operating at high Reynolds numbers and high angle of attacks make the accurate simulations of such complex flows still challenging. With recent advancements in High Performance Computing (HPC) clusters and parallel computing, the Lattice-Boltzmann Method (LBM) has emerged as an efficient and parallelizable algorithm for CFD simulations of complex flows. To understand the capabilities of LBM, flow over a circular cylinder can be used as a validation test case before more expensive simulations of complex separated flows around airfoils.

Flow fields around the cylinder at low Reynolds numbers have been widely researched in the literature. An early experimental study by Homann [1] observed that for very low Reynolds number values of $0 < Re < 4$, the streamlines are almost symmetrical in the vertical axis, and the flow remains attached to the surface of the cylinder. At about $Re = 6$, the onset of flow separation and the formation of attached vortices begin to appear behind the cylinder. As the Reynolds number increases, the flow becomes more separated, and the vortices continue to grow while remaining stable up until the Reynolds number of 30. Beyond this point, a further increase in Reynolds number is followed by instabilities in the flow, leading to the emergence of oscillatory flow patterns. The vortices behind the cylinder are shed from the cylinder alternately, resulting in a pattern of flow called the Kármán vortex street. Subsequent research by Roshko [2] demonstrated that this mode of flow, referred to as the stable range, continues until $Re = 150$. Reynolds numbers up until this point were also studied by Tritton [3], in which the findings of previous work were supported, and the slow appearance of additional modes about $Re = 100$ was investigated in detail. Beyond the threshold of $Re = 150$, the Kármán vortex street starts to exhibit irregular behaviour as it becomes more turbulent, and the flow starts to exhibit irregular behaviour. Turbulence sets in, eventually becoming a distinct wake at about $Re \approx 3 \times 10^5$.

Apart from experimental results, these findings were later reproduced with numerical simulations. Park [4] simulated the incompressible flow over a circular cylinder with high-resolution unsteady calculations up to $Re = 160$. Flow quantities, including Strouhal number, drag and lift coefficients, separation angle, and length of the separation bubble were calculated. Another numerical study was conducted by Qu [5] using the Finite Volume Method (FVM) to simulate the flow for Reynolds numbers 50 to 200, reporting the exact flow quantities as Park. Arumuga [6] conducted research, similar to the current study, performing flow simulations over a circular cylinder at moderate Reynolds numbers using an in-house Lattice-Boltzmann code. A range of Reynolds numbers from $Re=4$ to $Re=150$ are studied, effectively capturing both

steady-state and unsteady flow characteristics, thus providing an adequate benchmark for comparison. The drag coefficient was also calculated for both flow regimes and a comparative analysis was done with existing literature.

In this current study, the viscous flow over a circular cylinder as a validation test case using the Lattice-Boltzmann Method (LBM) with an open-source LBM code, OpenLB flow solver. Understanding the capabilities of LBM method and the parallel computational cost analysis of OpenLB code on TRUBA clusters will help to simulate more realistic but computationally expensive separated flows around rotary wing airfoils in the future. In this study, flow simulations around a cylinder are performed in parallel at Reynolds numbers ranging from 20 to 200 to observe both steady-state and unsteady flow characteristics by vortex shedding and the comparisons are done with the literature.

II. LATTICE-BOLTZMANN METHOD

Depending on the nature of the fluid flow, the governing fluid dynamics equations can be built on different physical assumptions that are determined by the relevant time and length scales. At the macroscopic scale, the motion or interaction of individual particles is insignificant. Then, the flow can be considered as a continuum by considering the average flow field quantities and is governed by the Navier-Stokes equations. Conventional CFD simulations seek approximate solutions to these equations. Conversely, at the microscopic scale, the interactions of individual particles are significant. In this case, the flow cannot be assumed as a continuum and is governed by Newtonian particle dynamics [7]. Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations for fluid flows are the microscopic scale methods. Between the Navier-Stokes based CFD simulations and the MD simulations, there are the mesoscopic scale methods. Between the macroscopic and microscopic scales, the flow is considered as a collection of ensembles. Each ensemble contains enough particles to make up a distribution of the flow field quantities. In the mesoscopic scale, the flow is governed by Kinetic theory [8] based on the statistical mechanics.

The Lattice-Boltzmann Method (LBM) is a family of methods that belong to the mesoscopic scale. Although relatively new when compared to the frequently used Finite Volume Method (FVM) or Finite Element Method (FEM), its origin can be traced back to being proposed as an alternative to Lattice-Gas Automata (LGA) method in 1988 [9].

Consider the Boltzmann equation for a system without external forces:

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla f = \Omega(f) \quad (1)$$

where, $f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, t)$ is the particle distribution function, \mathbf{v} is the particle velocity vector and Ω is the collision operator. Given the inherent complexity of the original form of the collision operator, various approximations are used for practical computations. A notable simplification of the collision operator was proposed by Bhatnagar, Gross, and Krook (BGK) [10] as follows:

$$\Omega = -\frac{1}{\tau} (f - f^{eq}) \quad (2)$$

where, τ is called the relaxation time parameter (inverse of collision frequency) and f^{eq} is the Maxwell-Boltzmann equilibrium distribution function.

In the Lattice-Boltzmann Method (LBM), the Boltzmann equation is discretized in time, space and velocity space using lattices. For the BGK collision operator, this discretization yields the streaming and collision calculations as:

$$f_i(\mathbf{x} + c_i \mathbf{e}_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = f_i(x, t) + \frac{\Delta t}{\tau} [f_i^{eq}(x, t) - f_i(x, t)] \quad (3)$$

where,

$$f_i^{eq} = \rho w_i [1 + 3c_i \mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{v} + 9/2(c_i \mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{v})^2 - 3/2(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{v})^2] \quad (4)$$

Commonly used D2Q9 lattice discretisation of velocity is shown in Figure-1. The respective discrete velocities are defined as in Table-I.

Fig. 1. D2Q9 Velocity Set at a Lattice Node [7]

TABLE I
DISCRETE VELOCITIES OF D2Q9 SET

Direction \mathbf{e}_i	Magnitude c_i	Weights w_i
(0, 0)	0	4/9
(1, 0), (0, 1), (-1, 0), (0, -1)	1	1/9
(1, 1), (-1, 1), (-1, -1), (1, -1)	$\sqrt{2}$	1/36

Macroscopic quantities such as density ρ and momentum $\rho \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are then calculated as the moments of the distribution function as

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{i=0,8} f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (5)$$

$$\rho \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{i=0,8} c_i \mathbf{e}_i f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (6)$$

This computational process can be divided into two distinct phases: collision and streaming. During the collision phase, the algorithm calculates the mass density and macroscopic velocity, resulting in the equilibrium distribution function f_i^{eq} and the post-collision distribution function f_i^* . The following streaming phase involves transferring the post-collision distribution to the adjacent nodes [7], which is a one-time step in the process.

III. LBM SIMULATIONS

The present study investigates the dependency of the drag coefficient and Strouhal number on the Reynolds number for the flow around a 2-D cylinder. To achieve variations in the Reynolds number, the inlet velocity is adjusted while keeping the geometry and fluid properties shown in Table-II unchanged. Furthermore, the same time step and grid size are selected for the Reynolds numbers used so that the lattice discretization is fine enough for all cases. The D2Q9 lattice velocity set and BGK model with the time relaxation parameter of $\tau = 0.56$ are used. The simulations are conducted for the total simulation time of 1500 seconds for all cases, which is deemed sufficient to collect enough samples of unsteady behaviour. An open-source parallel LBM code, the OpenLB [11] flow solver written in C++, MPI, OpenMP, and CUDA, is used for the simulations.

TABLE II
FLUID PROPERTIES

Property	Value	SI Unit
Density ρ	1.0×10^0	$[kg/m^3]$
Kinematic Viscosity ν	6.25×10^{-3}	$[m^2/s^1]$
Viscosity μ	6.25×10^{-3}	$[Pa.s]$

A. Computational Domain and Lattice Grid

For the LBM simulations, a 2D rectangular computational domain ($40D \times 30D$) is generated as shown in Figure-2. The solution domain is discretized into uniform cartesian mesh with $\Delta x = D/40$ with a total of 1.92 million lattices (1600×1200). For the physical simulation time of $t_{end} = 1500$ s for all cases, the total number of time steps is 7.5×10^5 in the unsteady simulations, where the time step for all Reynolds numbers is used as $\Delta t = 2 \times 10^{-3}$ s.

Fig. 2. Computational Domain

B. Boundary Conditions

Uniform velocity profile is enforced at the inlet, while the outlet is characterized by a Dirichlet pressure condition, set at $p = 0$. A fifth-order polynomial function is used to gradually

increase the inlet velocity up to its steady-state value. This increase continues until % 40 of the total simulation time after which it remains constant. This approach is adopted to ensure a smooth initialization of the flow for stability purposes. In LBM method, the wet-node type interpolated velocity and pressure boundary conditions are used for the inlet and outlet, respectively. The cylinder surface and walls of the domain are subjected to the no-slip boundary condition. For the domain walls at the top and bottom, a bounce-back boundary condition is implemented. For the curved cylinder surface, the Bouzidi [12] boundary condition is used.

C. Parallel Simulations on HPC

Hybrid parallelization is used in OpenLB. Lattices in the computational domain are partitioned into blocks and the Lattice blocks are distributed into computational nodes. Individual lattice blocks is parallelized via OpenMP in each node and MPI is used for communications between the nodes. Collision and streaming loops within a single block are automatically parallelized by OpenMP. Since the collision step is purely local and the streaming step only requires data of the neighboring nodes, parallelizing by spatial domain partitioning leads to low communication costs and is therefore efficient.

The parallel simulations are done on the Hamsi cluster on TRUBA, which has the computational nodes equipped with two Intel Xeon 6258R 2.70 GHz processors, each of which has 28 cores. The parallel simulations for all cases are performed on 28 cores. The parallel performance assessments are done by using different number of cores.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The LBM simulations are performed for steady-state and unsteady flow cases by using OpenLB flow solver and the results and computational costs are discussed in the following sections.

A. Steady-State Flow Simulations

As steady-state flow test cases, the LBM simulations are performed for $Re = 20$ and $Re = 40$ corresponding to the inlet velocity of $u_\infty = 0.125$ m/s and $u_\infty = 0.25$ m/s respectively. For $Re = 20$, the flow is observed to have already separated flow but steady-state behaviour. As the Reynolds number is increased to $Re = 40$, the separation point on the cylinder surface moves upstream, as shown in Figure-3 and Figure-4. Additionally, Figure-5 and Figure-6 depict the formation of attached vortices behind the cylinder in the wake. It is evident that as the Reynolds number increases, the size of the vortices grows, but they remain attached to the cylinder.

Figure-7 shows the variation of the drag coefficient as the flow develops and attains its steady-state value. The comparison between the drag coefficients for Reynolds numbers of 20 and 40 reveals that there exists an inverse relationship between the drag coefficient and the Reynolds number in this range of Reynolds number. The drag coefficient decreases as the Reynolds number increases. The general trend of the drag coefficient curve exhibits consistency.

Fig. 3. Velocity Contours at $Re = 20$

Fig. 4. Velocity Contours at $Re = 40$

Fig. 5. Streamlines around Cylinder at $Re = 20$

Fig. 6. Streamlines around Cylinder at $Re = 40$

Specifically, the drag coefficient initially experiences a gradual surge in response to the inlet velocity and attains its maximum value. After a slight dip, the coefficient stabilises at its steady-state value. The comparisons of drag coefficient C_d with previous studies from the literature are shown in Table-III. The results for two Reynolds numbers of 20 and 40 are presented and compared with the available experimental

results [3], other available LBM results [6], and the available CFD results [13, 14]. The current results compare well with the literature.

The length of the recirculation regions in the wake of the cylinder is measured as shown in Figure-5 and Figure-6. The non-dimensional recirculation length, $L_R = 2L/D$, shows consisted results with the literature [14-18] as can be seen in Table-IV

Fig. 7. Variation of Drag Coefficient with Time

TABLE III
COMPARISON FOR DRAG COEFFICIENT C_d

Author	Reynolds Number	
	20	40
Calhoun (Num.) [13]	2.19	1.62
Fornberg (Num.) [14]	2.00	1.50
Tritton (Exp.) [3]	2.22	1.48
Arumuga Perumal (Num.) [6]	2.25	1.50
Present LBM	2.20	1.62

TABLE IV
COMPARISON FOR RECIRCULATION LENGTH L_R

Author	Reynolds Number	
	20	40
Fornberg [14]	1.82	4.48
Coutanceau and Bouard [15]	1.86	4.26
He and Doolen [16]	1.84	4.49
Dennis and Chang [17]	1.88	4.69
Shu, Liu and Chew [18]	1.80	4.40
Present LBM	1.80	4.40

B. Unsteady Flow Simulations

To investigate unsteady flow characteristics, the LBM simulations are performed for two test cases with Reynolds numbers of $Re = 100$ and $Re = 200$. The corresponding inlet velocities are $u_\infty = 0.625$ m/s and $u_\infty = 1.25$ m/s. As the Reynolds number is increased from 20-40 to 100-200, the flow starts to become unsteady. The unsteadiness is evident in the form of alternately shed vortices trailing behind the cylinder. Figure-8 and Figure-9 shows the instantaneous snapshots of the flow with unsteady vortex shedding in the cylinder wake at $t = 1500$ s.

Fig. 8. Velocity Contours at $Re = 100$

Fig. 9. Velocity Contours at $Re = 200$

Fig. 10. Streamlines around Cylinder at $Re = 100$

Fig. 11. Streamlines around Cylinder at $Re = 200$

Figure-10 and Figure-11 shows the sinusoidal streamline patterns for both Reynolds numbers by using the relative velocities. It is noteworthy that, for the same distance behind the cylinder, the number of crests and troughs is greater for $Re = 200$ in comparison to $Re = 100$. This observation implies that the frequency of vortex shedding increases with Reynolds number. As vortices have a direct impact on the drag coefficient, the drag coefficient variation can be used to extract information about the shedding characteristics of the vortices.

The transient characteristics of the drag coefficient for both Reynolds numbers are depicted in Figure-12. The discrepancy

in the transient region of the curve is attributed to the difference in the inlet speed. As the inlet takes 40% of the total simulation time (equivalent to 600 s for both cases) to reach its maximum velocity, the velocity in simulation for $Re=200$ builds up more rapidly and enters the oscillatory region earlier than $Re=100$. In Figure-12, it is evident that the amplitude of oscillations is higher for $Re=200$ compared to $Re=100$.

A more detailed visualisation of the drag coefficient following the attainment of maximum velocity at the inlet is shown in Figure-13. The results indicate that the oscillatory frequency of the drag coefficient is increased at $Re = 200$. Furthermore, the mean value of the oscillatory drag coefficient is also delineated in Figure-13. Based on the mean values of the drag coefficient, it is observed that there is a slight increase in drag from $Re = 100$ to $Re = 200$. The comparisons of drag coefficient with the literature [5, 19-20] is presented in Table-V.

Fig. 12. Variation of Drag Coefficient with Time for the whole Simulation Time of 1500 s

Fig. 13. Drag Coefficient Variation Over Time - Zoomed View

To gain a better understanding of the vortex shedding characteristics, it is possible to transform the drag coefficient into the frequency domain using the Fast Fourier Transform,

as shown in Figure-14. In both Reynolds numbers, a singular dominant frequency can be easily identified by the peaks present on the frequency spectrum.

In addition, there are other vibration modes present, with a lower frequency than that of the main frequency and with relatively smaller amplitudes. The Strouhal number St , which is derived from the dominant frequencies of the drag coefficient as shown in Figure-14, is also compared with the literature [5, 19-21] in Table-VI.

TABLE V
COMPARISON FOR DRAG COEFFICIENT C_d

Author	Reynolds Number	
	100	200
Mittal [19]	1.322	1.327
Qu et al. [5]	1.319	1.316
Posdziech and Grundmann [20]	1.3504	1.3490
Present LBM	1.383	1.389

TABLE VI
COMPARISON FOR STROUHAL NUMBER St

Author	Reynolds Number	
	100	200
Mittal [19]	0.1644	0.1947
Qu et al. [5]	0.1649	0.1958
Posdziech and Grundmann [20]	0.1667	0.1976
Fey et al. [21]	0.1648	0.1951
Present LBM	0.1719	0.2024

Fig. 14. Drag Coefficient in Frequency Domain

C. Computational Performance

The simulations are done in parallel by using 28 CPU cores. The time step of $\Delta t = 0.002$ s and a uniform lattice size of $\Delta x = 0.025$ m with $N = D/\Delta x = 40$ are used

for all cases. Additionally, the frequency of writing the data is consistent across all simulations, with the drag coefficient being appended to a ".dat" file every 1 simulation second, and the remaining simulation data being recorded every 5 simulation seconds. The wall time required for the simulations are given in Table-VII for the test cases with different Reynolds numbers. The simulations are done for the same total simulation time of 1500 s with the same time step size and also with the same lattice size, thus showing similar wall clock time. As the Reynolds number increases, the characteristic length scale of the flow is expected to decrease and this requires refinement in the lattice size for accuracy while increasing the computational time. In this study, the lattice size is selected fine enough and used as the same for these low Reynolds numbers while investigating the flow characteristics.

On the other hand, in order to investigate the computational cost and efficiency of the Lattice-Boltzmann Method, a series of parallel computations is performed to examine the computational wall time while varying three key parameters: CPU core, lattice size, and time step. The performance of LBM is evaluated in order to determine the optimal combination of parameters for efficient simulations. In addition, in order to reduce the influence of data storage operations on the computational time, all data-saving procedures are executed at intervals of every 20 simulation seconds.

1) *Core Count*: In order to assess the parallel computational performance of LBM, the simulations of the following case are performed for different number of CPU cores.

- $Re = 100$
- Maximum Simulation Time = 800 s
- $\Delta x = 0.025$ and $\Delta t = 0.002$

The results are presented in Table-VIII and Figure-16. The computational wall time decreases as expected, as the number of cores increases from 1 to 28. In addition, Figure-17 shows the parallel speedup plot for this case. The LBM simulations have almost linear speedup for the given problem size until 16 cores, after that, it starts to deviate from the ideal linear curve.

2) *Lattice Size*: The lattice size ($D/\Delta x$) is changed from 0.05 to 0.00625 m ($D/20$ to $D/160$) to investigate the impact of problem size on the computational cost. By decreasing the lattice size, the problem size is increased resulting in an increase in the computational time as shown in Table-IX and Figure-18.

The simulations are done for the following test case:

- $Re = 100$
- Maximum Simulation Time = 800 s
- $\Delta t = 0.002$
- 28 CPU Core

As the lattice size decreases, the number of lattices per diameter (N) increases from 20 to 160. This improves the resolution on the cylinder wall and increases the total number of lattices in the computational domain. As expected, as the problem size increases, the total computation wall time also increases. As the Reynolds number increases further, the smaller

lattice size requirement will lead to larger problem sizes and higher computational costs for more realistic engineering problems.

3) *Time Step*: The following unsteady flow test case is used to test the effects of the time step size:

- $Re = 100$
- Maximum Simulation Time = 800 s
- $\Delta x = 0.025$
- 28 CPU Core

The resulting simulation times are presented in Table-X. As the time step size is decreased, the number of time steps required for the maximum simulation time will increase. This increases the computational wall time as seen in Figure-15.

TABLE VII
COMPUTATIONAL WALL TIME FOR DIFFERENT CASES

Reynolds Number	Wall Time [s]
20	3205.73
40	3197.72
100	3196.37
200	3180.89

TABLE VIII
VARIATION OF COMPUTATIONAL WALL TIME WITH # OF CPU CORE

# of CPU Core	Wall Time [s]	# of CPU Core	Wall Time [s]
1	39265.82	10	4379.68
2	19783.47	15	2908.98
4	10194.43	16	2739.37
5	8310.11	20	2243.84
8	5250.97	28	1694.99

TABLE IX
VARIATION OF COMPUTATIONAL WALL TIME WITH LATTICE SIZE

$D/\Delta x$	Wall Time [s]	$D/\Delta x$	Wall Time [s]
20	455.46	80	6560.09
40	1622.01	100	10337.33
50	2482.49	160	26243.65

V. CONCLUSION

The viscous flow over a circular cylinder is investigated by using the Lattice-Boltzmann Method flow solver OpenLB. The unsteady simulations are performed in parallel for different Reynolds numbers. The aerodynamic drag coefficient and Strouhal number are compared with the available data from the literature. Overall, the results of LBM simulations show good agreement for the low Reynolds numbers. The LBM

test cases are run with the selected parameters such as the lattice size and time step size. The computational cost and parallel performance analyses are done. With parallel LBM simulations, the flow characteristics around a cylinder can be captured accurately and efficiently for low Reynolds numbers. For higher Reynolds numbers of more realistic engineering flow problems, as the lattice size and time step size decrease, thus as the problem size increases, the computational cost of LBM simulations will continue to increase. However, with the help of the linear speedup characteristics, the flow simulations for cylinders and also for airfoils will be performed in the future by using LBM at higher Reynolds numbers.

TABLE X
VARIATION OF COMPUTATIONAL WALL TIME WITH TIME STEP

$1/\Delta t$	Wall Time [s]	$1/\Delta t$	Wall Time [s]
10	51.09	100	342.38
20	85.64	200	672.33
40	148.63	400	1453.47
50	178.83	500	1666.88
80	303.04	1000	3455.78

Fig. 15. Variation of Computational Wall Time with Time Step

Fig. 16. Wall Time Variation with Number of CPU Cores

Fig. 17. Speedup Factor Variation with Number of CPU Cores

Fig. 18. Variation of Computational Wall Time with Lattice Size

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This study was conducted using a modified version of the 2D Cylinder example distributed with OpenLB library, originally developed by Jonas Latt, Mathias J. Krause, Vojtech Cvrcek, Peter Weisbrod, Adrian Kummerländer. The original code is licensed under the GNU General Public License v2.0.

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